

Optimized Sequencing and Conflict-Free Path Planning for Arrival Flights during Runway Direction Changes

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Abstract—Runway direction changes frequently occur during real-world operations. When this happens, Air Traffic Control Officers (ATCOs) must resequence and guide affected arrival flights in the Terminal Manoeuvring Area (TMA) to align with the new runway direction. Currently, this task is manually performed by ATCOs, leading to prolonged runway direction transition times and excessive flight distances. To address this complex issue, this paper proposes a framework for sequencing and conflict-free path planning for arrival flights. Heuristic methods are adopted to meet the high timeliness requirements of this problem: Genetic algorithm is adopted to solve the arrival sequencing model, and the A* algorithm is used to search for the optimal path. 16 valid runway direction change scenarios were extracted from the ADS-B data of Singapore Changi Airport in May 2024 to validate the effectiveness of the proposed model and algorithm, with the number of flights ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 9. The experimental results show that the method proposed in this paper is computationally efficient, and results can be obtained within 1 second for any given scenario. In all scenarios, the time of the last flight passing through the merging point in the optimized results is earlier than the corresponding value in the historical data, with an average improvement of 240 seconds. This indicates that the method proposed in this paper can shorten the transition time for runway direction changes. In addition, compared to the historical data, the time for each flight to reach the merging point is advanced by 120 seconds on average in the optimized results. This indicates that the method proposed in this paper can find shorter flight paths than those implemented by the controllers, while ensuring conflict-free operation. Although the method proposed in this paper demonstrates outstanding performance in the laboratory phase, further validation of ATCO acceptance is required for practical implementation.

Keywords—Air traffic management; Terminal maneuvering area; Runway direction change; Arrival sequencing; Path planning; Genetic algorithm; A* algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

Runway is a critical resource in the air transportation system, serving as a vital link between airspace and the airport. The arrival traffic flows from different directions eventually converge into a single stream at the final approach leg. Afterward, aircraft maintain the required horizontal separation and land sequentially. The first systematic study on arrival flight sequencing can be traced back to 1976 [1].

This pioneering work investigated the system properties of using a first-come, first-serve policy, as well as those associated with optimization objectives aimed at maximizing throughput and minimizing delay. A decision methodology termed Constrained Position Shifting (CPS) is proposed to eliminate the undesirable properties inherent in these strategies. Another representative study introduced the concept of Receding Horizon Control (RHC) to address the dynamic arrival flight sequencing problem [2], which significantly reduces the computational burden. Building upon the two studies mentioned above, subsequent research has primarily focused on improvements to the optimization models [3], [4] and enhancements to the solution algorithms [5], [6]. These studies all assume that the Estimated Landing Times (ELTs) of all flights are known and focus on optimizing their landing sequence on the runway.

The ELT of an arrival flight is related to its entry time into the Terminal Maneuvering Area (TMA) and its flight path within the TMA. Arrival flights in the TMA typically follow Standard Terminal Arrival Routes (STARs) until the Initial Approach Fix (IAF) [7]. The path lengths and speed requirements of different STARs vary, and some studies [8], [9] take these differences into account when estimating the Estimated Landing Time (ELT) of flights. In addition to considering the required safety separation between flights on the runway, conflicts between flights at shared waypoints on different STARs are also taken into account [10]–[12]. Assuming all flights strictly follow the horizontal path of the STAR, the flight distance within the TMA is fixed, and in this case, the ELT can only be adjusted by placing flights in holding patterns or implementing speed control. However, the STAR is relatively short, so implementing speed control has limited impact on ELT, and holding patterns also have capacity constraints. To ensure that landing times meet the required safety separation [13], the Air Traffic Control Officers (ATCOs) will, when necessary, vector aircraft off the STAR to achieve more flexible flight times [14]. The analysis of historical data also indicates that flight trajectories within the TMA do not strictly follow the STARs [15], [16].

To enhance the practical applicability of optimization re-

sults, some studies have started to consider allowing slight deviations from the STAR during arrival sequencing. The historical flight trajectories that differ from the STARs are extracted as the flights' alternative arrival routes [14]. Turning legs and parallel legs were designed to achieve route stretching [17]. The subsequent two studies [18], [19] extended this research by providing turning legs with more options for flexibility. Another strategy is to ask the flight to fly directly to a specified point (usually a point on the STAR), achieving a route shortening by bypassing certain segments of the STAR [20], [21]. Despite the rich body of research on arrival sequencing, there remains a research gap in handling arrival sequencing and flight path planning when the STAR is completely unavailable. A typical scenario is when the runway direction changes, which is quite common in actual operations. An analysis of the historical flight trajectories at Singapore Changi International Airport (ICAO: WSSS) in May 2024 shows that on one day, there were up to four runway direction changes, with one case affecting as many as nine arrival flights.

When the runway direction changes, the STARs for the old runway direction can no longer be used, and flights already within the TMA are unable to join the STAR for the new runway direction. These flights must be fully radar-guided by ATCOs, leading to increased workload for both ATCOs and pilots. Moreover, human limitations can result in excessive flight distances and prolonged transition times to complete the runway direction change. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first attempt to address the problem of arrival sequencing and path planning when the runway direction changes. The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A framework for arrival sequencing and path planning during runway direction changes is proposed. The approach can be easily adopted to any other TMAs with limited calibrations.
- An efficient solution algorithm is designed to meet the demands of real-time computation. Heuristic methods were designed based on the problem characteristics in both the arrival sequencing and flight path planning modules, satisfying the computational time constraints of this tactical-level decision-making problem.
- This method can handle the challenge of simultaneously shortening the transition time for runway direction changes and minimizing the number of turns in the flight trajectories, while ensuring that safety separation requirements are met between any pair of flights at any given time.

The paper is organized as follows. Firstly, Section II describes the main challenges of arrival sequencing and path planning during runway direction changes and presents the solution proposed in this study. Subsequently, Section III presents the problem formulation for arrival sequencing and path planning models. Then, Section IV provides a detailed description of the experimental setup. Section V discusses the computational results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND OVERVIEW

When the runway direction changes, the ATCO needs to reassign landing sequences for all arrival flights and guide them to the merging point corresponding to the new runway direction. Therefore, two problems need to be addressed. The first is arrival sequencing, and the second is flight path planning.

When sequencing arrival flights, it is necessary to know the earliest and latest time each flight can reach the merging point from its current position. The earliest time a flight can reach the merging point mainly depends on three factors:

- 1) The earliest available time of the merging point. After the decision to change the runway direction is made, a certain amount of time is usually required to complete tasks such as runway surface inspections and activation of navigation aids before the new runway direction becomes available. During this period, the runway is unavailable.
- 2) The minimum flight time required for the flight to reach the merging point from its current position in the horizontal plane. This takes into account the shortest flight distance from the current position to the merging point and the flight's speed.
- 3) The minimum time required for the flight to descend from its current altitude to the specified altitude at the merging point. This requires considering the altitude difference between the flight's current altitude and the target altitude, as well as the Rate Of Descent (ROD).

The latest time a flight can reach the merging point is mainly constrained by the remaining fuel. The primary objective of arrival sequencing during runway direction changes is to land all arriving flights currently in the TMA as quickly as possible to minimize the adverse effects caused by the runway direction change.

Flight path planning generates the trajectory from the flight's current position to the merging point, ensuring the flight arrives according to the predetermined sequence. The primary objective of flight path planning is to minimize the flight distance. Additionally, every turn requires the ATCO to issue instructions to the pilot, who must then execute them, increasing the workload for both parties. Therefore, the fewer turns the generated trajectory requires, the better. Flight path planning is mainly constrained by the following three factors:

- 1) The heading of the flight upon reaching the merging point must meet certain requirements. For example, if the merging point is located on the final approach segment, the flight's heading at the merging point should align with the runway direction.
- 2) The flight must meet the required turn radius when making turns. The turn radius depends on the flight's speed and bank angle. With a constant bank angle, the higher the flight speed, the larger the required turn radius.
- 3) At any given time, the distance between two flights must satisfy the minimum safety separation requirement [7]. Within the TMA, both wake turbulence separation and radar separation need to be considered.

To address the aforementioned issues, this paper proposes a framework consisting of three main modules:

a) *Initial Path Planning*: This module is to find the shortest path from the current position to the merging point for arrival flights, satisfying all time requirements for reaching the merging point, and thereby determining the earliest time the arrival flights can reach the merging point.

b) *Arrival Sequencing*: This module uses the time at which each flight reaches the merging point as the decision variable (with the lower bound of the decision variable being the earliest time output by Initial Path Planning). It outputs the flight sequences at which flights pass the merging point, satisfying the safety separation constraints and corresponding to the optimal objective function value.

c) *Conflict-Free Path Planning*: This module treats the flight sequence output by Arrival Sequencing as the priority order for the flights and plans the path for each flight accordingly. When planning the path for a given flight, it must not conflict with the paths of flights with higher priority.

The relationships between these modules are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The diagram of the proposed approach for arrival sequencing and routing problem when the runway direction changes.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Grid Network and Initial Conditions

This work establishes a grid network for TMA to facilitate path planning. The newly established grid coordinate system

takes the new runway direction and its corresponding merging point as the positive x-axis and origin. The positive y-axis is oriented 90 degrees anticlockwise from the positive x-axis. The width of the grid can be defined as needed based on the problem requirements. Figure 2 presents an example of TMA discretization.

Figure 2. The grid network constructed for TMA.

This paper plans flight trajectories within a grid network environment, where the start node is one of the four vertices of the grid cell currently occupied by the flight, and the destination is the origin of the grid network. The vertex among the four candidates that requires the smallest heading change for the flight to reach is selected as the start node. Among the two possible headings at this vertex, the one closest to the flight's track angle upon arrival at that point is chosen as the start heading. An example of selecting the start node and start heading is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Start node and heading selection. The angular relationships are as follows: 1) $\theta_1 < \theta_4 < \theta_2 < \theta_3$; 2) $\varphi_2 < \varphi_1$.

B. Initial Path Planning

Given the outstanding performance of the A* algorithm in solving unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) path planning problems in large grid environments [22], this paper employs the A* algorithm to address the Initial Path Planning problem. The cost function design and neighbor expansion are the two core components of the A* algorithm.

a) *Cost function design*: The cost function is used by the A* algorithm to evaluate the priority of nodes. The A* algorithm always selects the node with the smallest cost function value for expansion, ensuring that the search progresses towards the optimal path. In this study, the cost function $f(n, d)$ for node n with heading d is expressed as follows:

$$f(n, d) = g(n, d) + h(n) \quad (1)$$

where $g(n, d)$ represents the actual cost function, which refers to the actual cost from the start node with start heading to node n with heading d . $h(n)$ represents the heuristic cost function, which estimates the expected cost from node n to the goal node.

The actual cost function $g(n, d)$ is typically designed to represent the number of grids traversed from the start node with start heading to node n with heading d . In the flight path planning problem, in addition to minimizing the path distance, it is also desirable to minimize the number of turns, see Figure 4.

Figure 4. Actual cost. There are two paths from the start point to the goal point, shown in red and green. Both paths have the same length, but the red path involves seven turns, while the green path only has one. In the flight path planning problem, the green path is more suitable.

Therefore, the actual cost function $g(n, d)$ is designed as follows:

$$g(n, d) = l(n, d) + t(n, d) \quad (2)$$

where $l(n, d)$ denotes the number of nodes traversed from the start node with start heading to node n with heading d . $t(n, d)$ denotes the number of turns that have occurred from the start node with start heading to node n with heading d .

The heuristic cost function is often represented by the Manhattan distance in grid-based network environments, which estimates the expected shortest distance from the current node to the target node. In the flight path planning problem presented in this paper, the distance constraint must be considered, meaning that the generated path length must not be shorter than the required distance D :

$$D = \frac{v_0 + v}{2} \times t_V + \max(t_E - t_V, 0) \times v_0 \quad (3)$$

where v_0 is the initial speed of the flight. v is the required speed at the merging point. t_V is the time required for the flight to descend from the current altitude to the required altitude at the merging point. This paper assumes that the

flight maintains its initial altitude and initial speed in level flight until it begins its descent, during which it decelerates uniformly to the required speed at the merging point. According to the kinematic formula for uniform deceleration, the distance required for the flight during its descent is $\frac{v_0 + v}{2} \times t_V$. t_E is the time interval between the moment when the decision to change the runway direction is made and the moment when the merging point becomes available.

The designed heuristic cost function incorporates an additional bias term based on the Manhattan distance to ensure that the path length exceeds a specified value:

$$h(n) = Manh(n) + \alpha \times b(n) \quad (4)$$

where $Manh(n)$ denotes the Manhattan distance from the current node n to the target node. As mentioned before, the coordinates of the target node are $(0, 0)$. Let the coordinates of node n be denoted as (x_n, y_n) , then $Manh(n) = |x_n| + |y_n|$. The value of α determines the unit penalty when the current possible shortest path length is less than the required distance D . The expression for the bias $b(n)$ is as follows:

$$b(n) = \max(D/L - l(n, d) - Manh(n), 0) \quad (5)$$

where $\max(x, y)$ is a function that selects the maximum value between x and y . L is the grid width.

b) *Neighbor expansion*: Whenever the algorithm selects a node for expansion, it generates all neighboring nodes of this node. These neighboring nodes represent the possible next states. In the flight path planning problem studied in this research, to avoid excessive turning angles, the maximum heading change for the flight at each node is limited to 90 degrees. At this initial stage of the study, the feasible turning angles for the flight at each node are set to discrete values: -90 degrees (right turn by 90 degrees), 0 degrees (maintaining current heading), and 90 degrees (left turn by 90 degrees). As a result, each node can have up to three neighboring nodes, which correspond to the positions obtained by moving one grid cell following all feasible turning angles, see Figure 5.

Figure 5. Neighboring nodes.

In the following two situations, some nodes may become unavailable:

- Grid boundary constraints. The next node is located outside the grid network. This often occurs at the edges of the established grid network.
- Turning limitations. The distance between the previous turning node and the current node is less than twice the turning radius. In this situation, the flight is restricted to maintaining its current heading.

C. Arrival Sequencing

This study considers an arrival merging problem in which a set of arrival flights \mathcal{F} must be sequenced to pass through a common merging point after a runway direction change. The goal is to minimize both the time when the last flight passes the merging point and the total delay time of all flights. The time horizon is discretized, and the merge time decision for each flight is modeled as an integer variable.

a) Decision Variables:

- $x_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$: Discrete time step when flight i reaches the merging point.
- $z \in \mathbb{Z}^+$: Auxiliary variable representing the latest merge time across all flights.
- $\gamma_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$: Binary variable indicating the sequencing order. $\gamma_{ij} = 1$ if flight i arrives before flight j , and 0 otherwise.

b) Parameters:

- e_i : Earliest allowed merge time for flight i .
- d_i : Maximum allowable delay for flight i after time T .
- T : Time when the runway direction change begins.
- s^r : Minimum radar separation distance (in nautical miles).
- $s^w(c_i, c_j)$: Minimum wake turbulence separation distance between flights i and j based on their categories c_i and c_j .
- v : Speed at the merge point (in nautical miles per second).
- β : Penalty coefficient for total flight delay.
- M : A large constant for big-M constraints.

c) *Objective Function*: The objective is to minimize the maximum merge time among all flights and the total delay, with the delay term inversely weighted to prioritize early arrivals:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \gamma, z} \quad z - \beta \sum_{i \in \mathcal{F}} \frac{1}{x_i - e_i + 1} \quad (6)$$

d) Constraints:

• Maximum Merge Time Definition:

Ensure that the auxiliary variable z correctly captures the latest merge time among all flights:

$$z \geq x_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F} \quad (7)$$

• Arrival Time Window:

Each flight must arrive within a feasible time window, which depends on its earliest possible arrival e_i and latest allowable time $T + d_i$:

$$x_i \geq e_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F} \quad (8)$$

$$x_i \leq T + d_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F} \quad (9)$$

• Sequencing Decision Variables:

For every flight pair (i, j) :

- One must precede the other:

$$\gamma_{ij} + \gamma_{ji} = 1, \quad \forall i \neq j \quad (10)$$

- A flight cannot precede itself:

$$\gamma_{ii} = 0, \quad \forall i \quad (11)$$

• Separation Requirements at the Merging Point:

These constraints ensure that aircraft i and j are sufficiently separated in time based on the sequencing variable γ_{ij} :

- Radar separation constraint:

$$x_j \geq x_i + \left\lceil \frac{s^r}{v} \right\rceil - M(1 - \gamma_{ij}), \quad \forall i \neq j \quad (12)$$

- Wake turbulence separation constraint:

$$x_j \geq x_i + \left\lceil \frac{s^w(c_i, c_j)}{v} \right\rceil - M(1 - \gamma_{ij}), \quad \forall i \neq j \quad (13)$$

• Variable Domains:

Define the type and range of each decision variable:

$$x_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad z \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad \gamma_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{F} \quad (14)$$

The proposed model is a Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) model. The MINLP nature of the problem makes it inherently NP-hard, as it involves combinatorial sequencing decisions and nonlinear temporal constraints, leading to exponential growth in solution space with the number of flights. Due to this computational complexity, solving the model to optimality using exact solvers becomes infeasible for large-scale or real-time applications. Therefore, heuristic or metaheuristic, are preferred to obtain high-quality solutions within acceptable computational times. Previous research by the authors has demonstrated the efficiency of Genetic Algorithm (GA) in addressing complex flight sequencing problems [23]. Therefore, this study employs a GA to solve the established MINLP model, and the pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 1.

D. Conflict-free Path Planning

Conflict-free path planning aims to generate flight trajectories sequentially, based on the output of the arrival sequence from Section III-C, i.e., the sequence and timing of flights passing through the merging point. In this context, the sequence of the flight represents its priority, where flight with earlier positions have higher priority. While planning the trajectory for each flight, the trajectories of higher-priority flights are treated as constraints, ensuring no conflict exists with any trajectory. Each time a flight path is planned, the following tasks need to be performed:

- 1) Update the arrival time of this flight at the merging point. Based on the required separation, compute the earliest time the next flight can reach the merging point. If this earliest time is later than the next flight's merging point time from Section III-C, the earliest time is converted into the next flight's required distance D . Otherwise, the merging point time from Section III-C is converted into the required distance D .
- 2) All nodes that the flight trajectory passes through, as well as the nodes within their neighborhoods (with a radius set to the radar separation), are added to the obstacle list. Time information for passing through each node is also recorded. The detailed logic can be found in Figure 6.

Algorithm 1 Arrival Sequencing Optimization via GA

Require:

Wake turbulence categories: $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$
 Earliest time over merging point: $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$
 Maximum allowable delay: $\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\}$
 Other parameters: T, s^w, s^r, v, β, M

Ensure:

Optimized time over merging point: $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$

Initialization:

for $i = 1$ to n **do**

Set lower bound: $lb_i \leftarrow e_i$

Set upper bound: $ub_i \leftarrow T + d_i$

end for

Set encoding type: real-valued

Set population size: N

Set maximum generations: G_{\max}

Objective Function Evaluation:

for each individual solution $X^{(k)} = \{x_1^{(k)}, \dots, x_n^{(k)}\}$ **do**

Sort $X^{(k)}$ in ascending order to obtain $X_{\text{sorted}}^{(k)}$

for each adjacent pair (i, j) in $X_{\text{sorted}}^{(k)}$ **do**

Retrieve original indices: $o(i)$ and $o(j)$

Separation: $s_{ij} = \max(s^w(c_{o(i)}, c_{o(j)}), s^r)/v$

if $x_j^{(k)} - x_i^{(k)} < s_{ij}$ **then**

Assign a large penalty to $X^{(k)}$

continue to next individual

end if

end for

Compute objective value:

$$f(X^{(k)}) = \max(X^{(k)}) - \beta \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i^{(k)} - e_i + 1}$$

end for

Evolution Process:

for $g = 1$ to G_{\max} **do**

Select parents

Apply crossover and mutation to generate offspring

Evaluate offspring using f

Select individuals for next generation via elitism

end for

Output the best feasible individual X^* with minimum objective value $f(X^*)$

As in the initial path planning module, the conflict-free path planning also adopts the A* algorithm to search for the optimal path. The two approaches adopt the same cost function, with the primary difference lying in the neighbor expansion process.

In the neighbor expansion process of Conflict-free Path Planning, it is necessary to consider not only grid boundary constraints and turning limitations but also potential conflicts with the trajectories of other flights. As shown in Figure 6, each generated conflict-free trajectory is converted into a set of obstacles, which is used for conflict detection during the neighbor expansion of subsequent flights. If a neighboring

Figure 6. Obstacle generation. For a given trajectory (green line with arrow), all nodes within the neighborhood (red circle) of each trajectory node are added to the obstacle list, along with their time information. The time information for all nodes within the neighborhood of a trajectory node is the same, and it is equal to the time of that trajectory node.

node is within the obstacle list, it is necessary to further check whether a temporal conflict exists. Considering the priority of flights, if two flights share the same node, the flight with a lower priority must pass through the node after the higher-priority flight. Therefore, the earliest available time for this neighboring node equals the latest appearance time of the obstacle at this point plus a safety buffer, i.e., $\max(s^r/v, s^w(c_i, c_j)/v)$. If the time a flight reaches the point from the start at the fastest possible speed (maintaining its initial speed) is later than the earliest available time, then the point is considered a feasible neighboring node.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETTING

This study extracts scenarios of runway direction changes from ADS-B data of flights arriving at and departing from Singapore Changi Airport (ICAO: WSSS) in May 2024 to verify the effectiveness of the proposed model and algorithm. Scenarios with only one arrival flight were excluded, resulting in 16 valid scenarios, with the number of flights ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 9.

The grid width is set to 0.5 nautical miles, the turn radius is set to 2.5 nautical miles (corresponding to a speed of 300 knots and a bank angle of 25 degrees), and the ROD is set to 1000 feet per minute. According to STAR requirements, the altitude restriction at the IAF is 3000 feet when the runway operates towards the south, and 4000 feet when the runway operates towards the north. The speed restriction at each IAF is 190 knots. This study adopts the altitude and speed restrictions at the IAF points as the altitude and speed restrictions for the merging point. The radar separation in the TMA is 3 nautical miles, and wake turbulence standards follow RECAT-EU [13]. The value of α is set to 10, and the value of β is set to 1. The d_i for all flights is uniformly set to 30 minutes.

This paper uses the Elitism Genetic Algorithm (EGA) to solve the established arrival sequencing model. Real-value encoding is adopted, with the population size set to 100 and the maximum number of generations set to 500.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The arrival sequencing and path planning during runway direction changes is a tactical real-time decision-making problem, requiring the proposed method to have high computational efficiency. Therefore, we first analyze the time required

Figure 7. The number of flights and algorithm runtime for each scenario.

Figure 8. The time at which the last flight passes through the merging point in both the historical and optimized results.

by the proposed model and algorithm to solve real-world cases. Using Python programming on a standard Windows laptop with an i7-12700 CPU, the algorithm's runtime for each scenario was less than 1 second, the number of flights and algorithm runtime for each scenario are shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that the algorithm's runtime is positively correlated with the number of flights. This result indicates that the proposed method can quickly solve the arrival sequencing and path planning problems. The computation time meets the timeliness requirements of the tactical phase, demonstrating potential for practical applications.

As described in Section III-C, the primary objective when the runway direction changes is to minimize its adverse effects. The faster the affected flights land on the new runway, the smaller the adverse effects caused by the runway direction change. For any scenario, comparing the time of the last flight passing the merging point between the optimized results and

Figure 9. Algorithm iteration trend (A N2S scenario).

Figure 10. Planned flight paths and the historical flight trajectories (A N2S scenario). The dashed lines represent the historical flight trajectories, while the solid lines represent the trajectories planned by the method proposed in this study. Different colors are used to distinguish between different flights. The historical flight sequence is as follows: IGO1005-SIA605-SIA447. The optimized sequence in this study is as follows: SIA447-SIA605-IGO1005.

historical data can reflect the improvement of the proposed method on this metric. To ensure a fair comparison, the earliest available time of the merging point for the new runway direction in each scenario is set to the time of the earliest flight passing that point in the historical data. In each scenario, the latest time for flights to arrive at the merging point in the optimized results is earlier than the corresponding value in the historical data, with an average improvement of 240 seconds per scenario. The detailed results for each scenario are shown in Figure 8. In addition, the flight time for each flight within the TMA was reduced by an average of 120 seconds. This indicates that the proposed method significantly outperforms the experience-based decisions made by ATCOs.

For each runway direction, a scenario was selected for detailed analysis. First, we analyze a case involving three flights where the runway direction changed from northbound to southbound (N2S). Figure 9 shows the algorithm iteration process for solving the arrival sequencing model using EGA. It can be seen that the algorithm converges within the first 100 generations, demonstrating the efficiency of EGA in solving this problem. The planned flight paths compared with the historical flight trajectories are shown in Figure 10. The time when the last flight passed the merging point was advanced by 79 seconds. The flight time for each flight within the TMA was also reduced by an average of 35 seconds. This indicates that relying on ATCO's experience for arrival sequencing and trajectory planning may not yield the optimal solution. In addition, each flight's historical trajectory involved a greater number of turns, and there is a case where flight flew out of

the TMA, i.e., SIA447, which further increases ATCO's monitoring and coordination workload. The trajectories planned in this study have fewer turns than the historical ones and are strictly within the TMA. Therefore, using the trajectories planned in this study can reduce the workload of both ATCOs and pilots.

Figure 11. Algorithm iteration trend (A S2N scenario).

The other scenario involves five flights, where the runway direction changes from southbound to northbound (S2N). As shown in the iterative process of the algorithm in Figure 11, the algorithm does not begin to converge until close to the 300th generation. This indicates that as the number of flights

increases, the number of evolutionary generations required for the algorithm to converge also increases. The planned flight paths compared with the historical flight trajectories are shown in Figure 12. The time when the last flight passed the merging point was advanced by 280 seconds. The flight time for each flight within the TMA was also reduced by an average of 131 seconds. Similar to the previous scenario, the historical trajectories in this scenario also have more turns than the trajectories planned in this study, and there is also an instance where flight flew out of the TMA.

The experimental results above demonstrate that the method proposed in this study can quickly sequence and plan the paths of affected flights when the runway direction changes. Compared to the historical flight trajectories, the results of this study show significant advantages in reducing the impact of runway direction change, minimizing flight time within the TMA, and reducing the number of turns. The proposed method can provide decision support for ATCOs, thereby reducing their workload and improving air traffic control operational efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a framework for arrival sequencing and conflict-free routing during runway direction changes. The framework consists of three main modules: Initial Path Planning, Arrival Sequencing, and Conflict-Free Path Planning. The Initial Path Planning module generates the shortest path from the current position of the flight to the merging point associated with the new runway direction, with objectives

of minimizing path length and the number of turns, while considering heading and turn radius constraints. This module also provides the earliest time for the flight to reach the merging point. The Arrival Sequencing module takes this time as a key input and outputs the optimal flight sequence and times to pass the merging point, aiming to minimize airspace occupancy and flight delays while considering time window constraints and safe separation requirements. Finally, the Conflict-Free Path Planning module takes the output from Arrival Sequencing module as input, incorporating path conflict constraints to produce globally conflict-free flight paths. Experimental results show that the proposed method can quickly generate optimal flight sequences and conflict-free paths, reducing airspace occupancy, flight time in the terminal area, and the number of turns for arrival flights.

Future research will explore more heading change options to enhance the flexibility of path planning. Additionally, by incorporating altitude considerations, the current two-dimensional path planning model will be extended to a three-dimensional model, further improving the general applicability of the proposed method.

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Figure 12. Planned flight paths and the historical flight trajectories (A S2N scenario). The dashed lines represent the historical flight trajectories, while the solid lines represent the trajectories planned by the method proposed in this study. Different colors are used to distinguish between different flights. The historical flight sequence is as follows: SIA735-QTR944-SIA431-TGW303-AXM1729. The optimized sequence in this study is as follows: QTR944-AXM1729-TGW303-SIA735-SIA431.

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